

Structured catalysts for carbon dioxide hydrogenation to methanol

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Abstract

In the literature review section, this study provided a concise overview of the heterogeneous catalytic hydrogenation process of converting carbon dioxide into methanol. It discussed commonly employed reactors and catalysts, delving into an examination of various anodization processes and catalyst coating methods. Subsequently, the most suitable methods were identified for implementation in the experimental phase.

In the experimental phase, several Cu/Zn-catalysts were synthesized using the wet-impregnation method. These catalysts were then applied in experiments involving the CO₂ hydrogenation process within a pressurized fixed bed reactor. The key variables under investigation were reaction temperature and volumetric flow rate. By calculating conversion, selectivity, yield, and specific activity, the effectiveness of the catalysts could be accurately assessed.

The results demonstrated the capability of the produced catalysts to perform methanol production via CO₂ hydrogenation. However, it was apparent that the competing reaction, the reverse water-gas shift, had a dominant influence under the chosen experimental conditions. The best outcomes for methanol production were observed at lower temperatures and flow rates.

Keywords CO₂ hydrogenation, methanol, carbon dioxide, copper, catalyst, impregnation

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Tiivistelmä

Tämän työn kirjallisuuskatsauksessa annettiin tiivis yleiskatsaus hiilidioksidin heterogeeniseen katalyyttiseen hydraukseen metanoliksi. Työssä käsiteltiin myös yleisesti käytettyjä reaktoreita ja katalyyttejä sekä tarkasteltiin erilaisia anodisointiprosesseja ja katalyyttipinnoitusmenetelmiä. Tämän perusteella valittiin sopivimmat menetelmät kokeellista osuutta varten.

Kokeellisessa osuudessa tuotettiin useita Cu/Zn -katalyyttejä, käyttäen märkäimpregnointimenetelmää. Näitä katalyyttejä käytettiin kokeissa, joissa hiilidioksidin hydrausta metanoliksi tutkittiin paineistetussa kiintopetireaktorissa. Tärkeimmät muuttujat, joihin keskityttiin, olivat reaktion lämpötila ja tilavuusvirtaus. Laskemalla konversio, selektiivisyys, saanto ja spesifinen aktiivisuus voitiin arvioida katalyyttien tehokkuutta.

Tulokset osoittivat, että valmistetut katalyytit kykenivät edistämään metanolin tuotantoa hiilidioksidin hydrauksessa. Oli kuitenkin selvää, että kilpaileva reaktio, käänteinen vesikaasun siirtoreaktio, vaikutti vallitsevasti valituissa kokeellisissa olosuhteissa. Parhaat tulokset metanolin tuotannolle saavutettiin matalammilla lämpötiloilla ja virtausnopeuksilla.

Avainsanat CO₂ hydraus, metanoli, hiilidioksidi, kupari, katalyytti, impregnointi

Preface

This master's thesis was done for VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, and it was a part of EU funded UP-TO-ME project, with a goal of targeting a change in decentralized Power-to-Methanol production for hard to electrify applications.

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Henri Hopeasaari

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Abbreviations and symbols

Abbreviations

AAO	Anodized aluminium oxide
BWR	Boiling water reactor
ECD	Electrochemical deposition
ELP	Electroless deposition
GC	Gas chromatograph
HWT	hot water treatment
PWT	pore widening treatment
RDP	Reduction Deposition Precipitation
rWGS	Reverse water-gas shift reaction
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
STP	Standard temperature and pressure, 273 K and 1.013 bar
TOS	Time on stream

Symbols

ΔH°	[kJ mol ⁻¹]	Enthalpy of reaction
$C_{balance}$	-	Elemental carbon balance
df	-	Degrees of freedom
$H_{balance}$	-	Elemental hydrogen balance
\dot{n}	[mol min ⁻¹]	Molar flow rate
N	-	Observations
$O_{balance}$	-	Elemental oxygen balance
R^2	-	R Square
S	-	Selectivity
SA	[g gcat·h ⁻¹]	Specific activity
$V_i\%$	-	Volumetric percentage of component i
V_m	[L mol ⁻¹]	Molar volume
V_{tot}	[L min ⁻¹]	Total volumetric flow rate
X	-	Conversion
Y	-	Yield

1 Introduction

The increasing levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the earth's atmosphere has become a major environmental concern in the modern world, as it greatly contributes to global warming and climate change [1]. One approach to lessen the impact of said emissions is to capture and utilize CO₂ as a feedstock to produce valuable chemicals. Among the various conversion pathways, CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol has gained a significant attention due to its potential to address the challenges of carbon capture, utilization, and storage [2].

Methanol is a versatile chemical that can be used as a feedstock to produce wide range of different chemicals, and it can also be used as a clean-burning fuel in transportation, as well as in fuel cells for power production [3]. CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol provides a way to convert CO₂ into a valuable and renewable chemical that could replace fossil fuels and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

In recent years, significant progress has been made in the development of catalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol, as well as in the understanding of the reaction mechanism and the factors that affect the catalyst performance. The use of structured catalysts, which offer improved mass and heat transfer, as well as enhanced stability and selectivity, has also emerged as a potential approach for improving CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol [4].

1.1 Aim of the thesis

The primary objective of the literature review is to review CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol, with specific emphasis on the utilization of structured catalysts and the associated coating techniques employed to fabricate such catalysts.

The experimental section of this study aims to explore the most suitable catalyst coating methods identified in the literature review and apply it to an

anodized aluminium-based catalyst structure for fixed-bed reactors. The structured catalyst is evaluated against a conventional fixed bed reactor. This investigation seeks to gain insights into the performance and efficacy of the coating method for potential applications in CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol.

2 Catalysts and reactor designs in CO₂ hydrogenation process

2.1 CO₂ hydrogenation

Methanol formation from CO₂ and H₂ is an exothermic reaction and is favoured at high pressures and low temperatures. The CO₂ hydrogenation is a competing process between two reactions, the methanol synthesis reaction, which is presented in Equation 1, and the reverse water-gas shift reaction (rWGS) which is presented Equation 2.

The rWGS reaction occurs more at higher reaction temperatures, and it produces water and carbon dioxide (CO), and it can significantly reduce the selectivity of methanol, limiting the maximum reaction temperature for methanol synthesis applications. Since there is bound to always be some CO in the process, a third reaction occurs, where carbon monoxide hydrogenates to methanol, as shown in Equation 3 [5].

The most conventional catalysts used for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol are copper-based catalysts, specifically Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ [5]. Although new catalysts have been developed, these conventional ones are still widely researched for potential improvements. The most common approach to producing MeOH is by using a mixed gas feed of carbon monoxide and hydrogen, known as synthesis gas (syngas). However, this catalyst suffers from several technical issues when used to convert CO₂ to methanol directly, including low single-pass

conversion, low methanol selectivity, the need for high pressure, and quick deactivation caused by the reverse water gas shift reaction [6].

The process of converting CO₂ to methanol can also be simplified when using pure CO₂ and hydrogen sources, compared to the syngas method. This approach simplifies the chemistry and reaction products as there is less impurities present in the reaction [7].

The reactor design is important in methanol synthesis for preserving catalyst life, achieving acceptable production rate and quality, and controlling process conditions. Boiling water reactors or adiabatic reactors are used, but they come with their own challenges. High temperatures (>300 °C) in these reactors can lead to catalyst sintering, which shortens the effective life of the catalyst, thereby increasing the costs as the process must be interrupted for catalyst replacement or regeneration [8]. However, these problems are mitigated when synthesizing methanol from CO₂ and hydrogen, which results in a lower reaction temperatures, than existing methanol synthesis reaction routes [8]. This allows the use of a single tube-cooled reactor, which due to their direct contact with the cooling elements, distributes heat more evenly, preventing hot spots and thus minimizes catalyst sintering, thereby extending the useful life of the catalyst [7].

2.2 Process conditions

As mentioned before, producing methanol through the CO₂ hydrogenation pathway is favourable at high pressure and low temperatures. It has been indicated that the production of methanol is significantly limited under normal or low pressures [9]. However, the methanol yield can be improved by increasing the H₂ to CO₂ ratio and reaction pressure [10]. Consequently, the effectiveness of the methanol synthesis process is greatly influenced by key operating factors, including the reaction pressure, reaction temperature, and

composition of the feed gas (H_2/CO_2), resulting in significant impacts on the conversion of CO_2 and the product distribution [9].

2.2.1 Effect of reaction pressure

The synthesis of methanol through the CO_2 hydrogenation process exhibits favourability under elevated pressure conditions. Referring to Equations 1 and 3, the conversion of CO_2 and CO into methanol reduces the molecules in the process. In accordance with Le Châtelier's principle, these reactions are more favourable under increased pressure.

A lot of research has been focused on methanol synthesis via CO_2 hydrogenation at pressures over 350 bars. For instance, Bansode et al. [11] investigated the CO_2 hydrogenation reaction at a pressure of 360 bars. They reported a CO_2 conversion of 95% and a methanol selectivity of 98% under these conditions at a temperature of $260^\circ C$. Similarly, Gaikwad et al. [12] conducted methanol synthesis experiments at a pressure of 442 bars and achieved approximately 90% CO_2 conversion and 95% methanol selectivity at a temperature of $280^\circ C$. Thus, based on these studies, it can be concluded that reaction pressure significantly influences CO_2 conversion and methanol selectivity.

2.2.2 Effect of reaction temperature

Generally, as the reaction temperature rises, the reaction rate increases due to the heightened kinetic energy of molecules. The conversion of CO_2 to methanol, which is an exothermic reaction, is more favourable at lower temperatures, while the rWGS reaction is more favourable at higher temperatures [13]. Thus, striking a balance between these opposing reactions becomes crucial to achieve the best conversion of CO_2 to methanol.

Numerous studies have reported that methanol conversion initially increases,

as the reaction temperature rises, but then reaching a peak value. For instance, Xin et al. [14] observed that at 250°C, the methanol yield was 17%, which was 36% higher compared to the yield at 210°C, while maintaining pressure at 50 bar and space velocity at 6000 ml(g cat)⁻¹ · h⁻¹. The article concluded that 250°C was the optimal reaction temperature for maximizing methanol yield based on their experimental findings. However, as methanol synthesis is more temperature sensitive than the rWGS reaction, methanol yields start to decline above 250°C while CO yields begin to increase. Similarly, Qi et al. [15] made an observation, reporting that methanol yield increased with rising reaction temperature, with a claimed maximum yield of 15% at 240°C. Thus, basing on the current literature information, it can be concluded that the reaction temperature is a key factor influencing methanol yield and CO₂ conversion.

2.2.3 Effect of gas composition

As can be seen on equation (1), the stoichiometric molar ratio of H₂-to-CO₂ is 3:1. Consequently, a majority of laboratory studies have been performed with this ratio. However, to investigate the impact of the H₂/CO₂ molar ratio on CO₂ conversion and methanol selectivity, Bansode et al. [11] conducted experiments with varying ratios ranging from 3 to 14. These experiments were performed at a pressure of 360 bars and a temperature of 260°C. The obtained results indicated that up to H₂/CO₂ ratio of 10, the methanol selectivity and CO₂ conversion increased, while beyond this the change was trivial. Similarly, Ahmad et al. [16] explored the effect of the H₂/CO₂ molar ratio on methanol selectivity at a pressure of 1 bar and a temperature of 200°C. It was observed that methanol selectivity increased from 94% to 96% when the H₂/CO₂ molar ratio was increased from 3 to 9. Additionally, Zhang et al. [17] investigated the influence of the H₂/CO₂ ratio at a pressure of 30 bars and a temperature of 240°C. Their findings indicated that as the H₂/CO₂ molar ratio increased from 1 to 10, CO₂ conversion increased from 7% to 20%. However, methanol selectivity decreased from 81% to 75%.

2.3 Catalysts used in CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol

2.3.1 Metal catalysts

Metal catalysts are the most used catalyst type in methanol synthesis. Extensive research has been focused on investigating the role of copper as an active catalyst component [18]. Copper-based catalysts have been widely acknowledged as the most effective and discerning catalysts for the synthesis of methanol through CO₂ hydrogenation [18], [19].

Noble metals, namely platinum, palladium, gold, and silver have emerged as prominent catalysts in the field of catalysis owing to their extraordinary characteristics and exceptional catalytic performance [20]. However, noble metal catalysts are significantly more expensive compared to non-noble metal catalysts like copper. The high cost of noble metals is primarily due to their limited availability, coupled with the complex and resource-intensive processes involved in their extraction and purification. This cost disparity poses a challenge for industrial applications and motivates ongoing research on improving catalytic performance.

Most of the copper-based catalysts have been synthesized with various catalyst supports such as Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃, Cu/ZnO and Cu/ZrO₂ [21]. Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃, composed of 60 wt.% Cu, 30 wt.% ZnO, and 10 wt.%, is one of the most studied catalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol [22]. Al₂O₃ functions as a structural promoter, enhancing the mechanical stability, distribution of Cu and overall surface area of catalyst [22].

Fujimoto et al. [23] studied the utilization of Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst for the hydrogenation of CO₂ to methanol. Their findings indicated that the catalyst exhibited enhanced activity and stability, primarily attributed to the

stabilization of the zero-valent form of copper. It was also found that the zinc oxide played a notable role in alumina-based catalysts.

In one study using a fixed-bed reactor, CO₂ hydrogenation was conducted at 200°C and 9 bar pressure, utilizing a Cu/ZrO₂/ZnO catalyst. It was observed that the catalyst achieved higher CO₂ conversion but with relatively low selectivity for methanol [10]. Another recent study by Cai et al. [24] demonstrated improved CO₂ conversion and selectivity using Cu/Zn/Ga catalysts in a fixed-bed reactor. Furthermore, the effect of fluorine on Cu/Zn/Al catalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol in a fixed-bed reactor was examined [25]. The study revealed that fluorine-modified catalysts exhibited improved activity for methanol synthesis in the fixed-bed reactor setting.

Cu/ZnO is also extensively used catalyst for the methanol synthesis through CO₂ hydrogenation [26]. The presence of lattice oxygen vacancies in zinc oxide serves a dual purpose: enhancing the dispersion of copper and providing greater stability to the copper species. Additionally, the lattice electron pair of ZnO has been found to actively contribute to methanol production. The improved dispersion of copper and the formation of flat Cu species on the surface of zinc oxide result in heightened activity and selectivity towards methanol in the Cu/ZnO system. [27]

Nitta et al. [28] also observed similar outcomes, where the addition of ZnO increased the catalyst's surface area and improved copper dispersion, leading to enhanced activity even at lower temperatures. The strong interaction between Cu and ZnO further promotes the dispersion of the metal, enhancing the catalyst's redox profile and ultimately increasing its activity in methanol formation. Additionally, the strong synergy between Cu and ZnO is believed to make the Cu/ZnO catalyst more active than Cu/SiO₂ in CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol [29]. F. Arena et al. [30] have reported the promoting effect of ceria on CO₂ adsorption, leading to increased methanol activity over Cu-ZnO catalysts.

However, the most commonly used copper catalyst in carbon dioxide hydrogenation is reported to be Cu/ZnO/ZrO₂ [31]. Nitta et al. [28] reported that while zirconia works as a catalyst promoter, it also increases selectivity and activity of methanol synthesis, when it occurs with copper. They also reported that due to the good ion exchange capacity, and the plentiful availability of surface oxygen, makes zirconia excellent catalyst candidate for hydrogenation reactions generally.

Palladium (Pd)-based catalysts have been studied for methanol synthesis through the hydrogenation of carbon dioxide. Different supports, such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃, La₂O₃, and ThO₂, have also been explored with Pd-based catalysts for carbon dioxide hydrogenation to methanol [2]. Pd/La₂O₃ catalyst exhibited a higher methanol selectivity of approximately 90% under reaction conditions of 120 bar pressure and 350°C temperature [32]. Pd-In catalysts have also shown excellent activity, with a 70% higher methanol synthesis rate compared to the reference Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalysts [33]. Fan et al. [34] investigated Pd-based CeO₂ catalysts for carbon dioxide reduction to methanol and found that Pd/CeO₂ exhibited higher activity and longer lifetime when reduced at 500°C. Similarly, Pd/TiO₂, when reduced at a high temperature of 500°C, showed a strong interaction between the metal and support, resulting in higher activity and selectivity towards methanol. However, when reduced at 400°C, methane became the main product [35]. This highlights the importance of catalyst reducibility in determining the selectivity of Pd-based catalysts. Compared to Cu-based catalysts, Pd/ZnO catalysts were found to be less active for methanol synthesis from CO₂ reduction [35]. Furthermore, Pd-based catalysts exhibited higher selectivity towards methane, reducing methanol selectivity.

Several authors have investigated gold (Au)-based catalysts supported by various materials such as ZnO, Al₂O₃, ZrO₂, CeO₂, TiO₂, and In₂O₃ for methanol synthesis from CO₂. Hartadi et al. [36] found that the methanol selectivity of the Au/ZnO catalyst was significantly higher (70%) than that of the Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst (40%) under similar conditions. Another study noted

that the presence of gold increased the formation of undesired by-products, such as CO, at higher temperatures ($>250^{\circ}\text{C}$) during CO_2 hydrogenation [37]. Wu et al. [38] conducted a comprehensive study comparing the catalytic performance of Au-based catalysts supported by ZnO, ZrO_2 , CeO_2 , and TiO_2 in terms of methanol yield and selectivity. Among these catalysts, the ZrO_2 -supported Au catalyst exhibited the highest methanol yield at 140°C and 45 bar pressure. There have also been studies exploring the performance of In_2O_3 -supported Au-based catalysts. These catalysts demonstrated higher catalytic activity compared to ZnO, ZrO_2 , CeO_2 , TiO_2 , and Al_2O_3 -supported catalysts. In the presence of the In_2O_3 -supported Au catalyst, a methanol selectivity of 100% was achieved in the CO_2 hydrogenation reaction at 225°C and 50 bar pressure [39]. Lu et al. [40] studied the effect of temperature on methanol selectivity using In_2O_3 and In_2O_3 - ZrO_2 -supported Au catalysts at 50 bar pressure. It was found that at 225°C , the In_2O_3 - ZrO_2 -assisted catalyst exhibited 100% methanol selectivity, surpassing the performance of the In_2O_3 - ZrO_2 catalyst.

The role of silver (Ag) as an active component in methanol catalysts has received less attention compared to other noble metal catalysts. Ag is considered less active for methanol synthesis than Cu. However, the literature on the role of Ag is not consistent. Some studies have reported higher selectivity for Ag/ZrO_2 compared to Cu/ZrO_2 at low temperatures (below 227°C) in methanol synthesis [41]. Doping Cu/ZrO_2 with Ag has also been observed to enhance the selectivity of CO_2 hydrogenation to methanol without significantly affecting carbon dioxide conversion [42]. In specific reaction conditions, Rhodes et al. [43] found that silver catalyst achieved 100% methanol selectivity, while Cu/ZrO_2 exhibited selectivity between 75% and 90% in the same reaction. Similarly from the same study, Ag/ZrO_2 catalyst exhibited higher activity but lower selectivity to methanol compared to Ag/ZnO catalyst under the same reaction conditions. This suggests that the Ag/ZnO system shows higher selectivity to methanol than Ag/ZrO_2 under specific reaction conditions. It should then be noted that all Ag-based catalysts exhibited better selectivity, but lower activity compared to $\text{Cu}/\text{ZnO}/\text{ZrO}_2$, indicating that Ag is less active than Cu in CO_2 hydrogenation to methanol.

2.3.2 Structured catalysts

Structured catalysts, also known as coated catalysts, present a promising alternative to conventional heterogeneous particle catalysts. These catalysts are formed by applying a thin layer of catalyst onto the surface, which usually consist of either a metallic or ceramic structure [44]. The typical structure of coated catalyst can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The anatomy of structured catalyst prepared by coating, showing the different sections of the catalyst system. Reproduced from Montebelli *et al.* [44].

The use of structured catalyst allows the design and the use of more complex and favourable catalyst constructions, like the one seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conventional structured catalysts with different sizes of monolithic channels. Reproduced from Nijhuis *et al.* [45].

Monolithic catalysts were developed for automobile industry to be used as a catalytic treatment of exhaust gases. Because of the high volumetric gas flow, the reactor must have a low pressure drop, which structured catalysts can help with [45]. In conventional monoliths, the channels are typically straight, and the walls exhibit a smooth surface, which results in laminar flow conditions. Consequently, mass transport of reactants to the catalyst surface is primarily governed by diffusion [46]. To enhance the mass transfer, a more convoluted fluid flow path in the structure is needed, as this promotes a greater interaction between the reactants and the catalyst surface [46]. Other advantages of structured catalysts over traditional fixed beds, is the improved heat transfer [47]. In the latter, the transfer is confined only into the contact points, and the formation of stagnant zones, channelling effects and preferred pathways affects the heat transfer. As can be seen in the Figure 3. the structured shape of monoliths offers a more favourable path for the heat to dissipate [47].

Figure 3. The possible flow paths of reactants over randomly packed bed (left) and over structured (right). Reproduced from Gascon *et al.* [47].

Structured catalysts are contemporary technique in the field of heterogeneous catalysts. They have a high active surface area and high voidage, which limit the pressure drop, and can offer a good heat transfer [47]. But due to their higher production cost and the difficulty to scale-up, they still require plenty of research before they start to replace the traditional catalysts [48].

2.4 Reactor designs

2.4.1 Fixed-bed reactors

Fixed-bed reactors have been extensively used for gas phase reactions, and as a hydrogenation of CO₂ to methanol is usually synthesized in gas phase, fixed-bed reactor is a typical reactor candidate for this [49]. However, contrary to regular fixed-bed, in CO₂ hydrogenation, the unreacted gases may be needed to be recycled during the whole process, due to the slow nature of the reaction. Layout of said reactor can be seen in the Figure 4.

Figure 4. Reactor layout of fixed-bed reactor with recycling of unreacted gases. Reproduced from Eigenberger *et al.* [50].

In these reactors, the catalyst is arranged in a solid "fixed" manner, and the reactants pass over it. The MeOH synthesis reaction is often performed in an isothermal fixed bed reactor within a temperature range between 200 and 230 °C and a pressure between 50 and 80 bar [31]. Despite their widespread use, fixed-bed reactors can face issues with pressure drop across the catalyst bed due to the gas flow. Also, a potential drawback is the deactivation of catalysts when exposed to elevated temperatures of 300 °C for copper-based catalysts, over an extended period of reaction time. Fixed-bed reactor also suffers from

heat and mass transfer limitations due to the high exothermicity of the reaction and the formation of hot spots within the reactor bed, which can lead to suboptimal performance or even reactor damage [51].

2.4.2 Slurry reactors

Catalyst deactivation is a common drawback in industrial processes, and it can be caused by various factors such as poisoning, thermal degradation, compound formations, side reactions, fouling, and mechanical attrition/crushing [52]. In the case of exothermic reactions like CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol, catalyst deactivation can occur due to the heat generated during the reaction pathway. To prevent catalyst deactivation in copper catalysts, it is necessary to reduce the heat generated. One possible solution is to carry out the reaction in the liquid phase, where the heat generated can be absorbed by a reaction solvent with a high heat capacity. In addition to mitigating catalyst deactivation, the low-temperature liquid phase is thermodynamically favourable for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol [6].

Slurry reactors represent an alternative to fixed-bed reactors for methanol synthesis from CO₂ [53]. Instead of a fixed catalyst bed, in these reactors, nanosized catalyst particles are suspended in a liquid phase or "slurry." Slurry reactors can maintain isothermicity even under dynamically changing feed gas compositions, which is an advantage over certain fixed-bed reactors, like non-isothermal reactors [53]. Other advantages include low pressure drop as the gas and liquid phases are in a stirred mixture, resulting in lower energy consumption. Also, as the CO₂ hydrogenation is an exothermic reaction that can produce high amount of heat, the slurry reactor can battle against with their excellent heat transfer capabilities, thus preventing hot spots, thereby avoiding potential damage or deactivation of the catalyst. The use of slurry reactors can also allow for the use of catalysts with varying sizes and compositions. This enables the exploration of a broader range of catalytic materials and particle sizes, potentially leading to increased efficiency of the CO₂ hydrogenation

process [26]. In a study by Kim et al. [54], concluded that the use of slurry reactor instead of fixed bed increased selectivity of methanol, as well as the conversion of CO₂ over two times.

There are also some disadvantages in the use of slurry reactors, such as the difficulty in separating the catalyst particles from the liquid phase after the reaction, which can be time-consuming and may result in the loss of catalyst [11]. Slurry reactors also often face the problem of catalyst attrition due to constant agitation, which can lead to a decrease in catalyst activity over time and, consequently, a decrease in CO₂ conversion [55].

2.4.3 Fluidized-bed Reactors

Fluidized-bed reactors have emerged as an effective choice for this CO₂ hydrogenation process, offering benefits such as high reaction rates, uniform temperature distribution, and efficient heat transfer [55]. One of the main advantages of fluidized-bed reactors is their excellent heat and mass transfer characteristics, which are crucial for the highly exothermic reaction of CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol. The fluidized nature of the bed allows for a uniform temperature profile, reducing the risk of catalyst deactivation due to hot spots. The good contact between gas and solid particles in a fluidized-bed reactor promotes high reaction rates, contributing to its high performance in the CO₂ hydrogenation process [56].

There are also some disadvantages in this reactor type, such as attrition and erosion, because the catalyst particles are in constant motion. This reduces the catalyst's lifespan and necessitates frequent replacement or regeneration, contributing to higher operational costs. Designing and operating fluidized-bed reactors can be more complex than traditional fixed-bed reactors due to the dynamic nature of the fluidized bed. The multiphase flow behaviour in these reactors necessitates more advanced control strategies for efficient operation. One major challenge of fluidized-bed reactors is the possibility of gas

bypassing, where the reactant gases do not completely interact with the catalyst particles, leading to lower conversion efficiency. Additionally, dead zones, or areas with reduced catalyst movement, can occur, further affecting reactor performance [55].

3 Aluminium structures

Aluminium and aluminium alloys are often used in many application fields, especially construction, transportation, and electronical components, due to their excellent properties, like high strength-to-weight ratio and good conductivity [57]. Aluminium also shows a passivating behaviour, which offers naturally good corrosion resistance. To improve these properties even further on, an anodization treatment can be performed, to obtain a layer of aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3).

Aluminium was chosen as a catalyst lattice structure material for its practical features, like low cost, abundance, good thermal properties, and the ability to produce complex shapes with technologies like 3d-printing [58]. Anodizing involves an electrochemical technique in which the aluminium surface serves as the anode within an electrolytic cell. By application of an electrical current, the growth of aluminium oxide on the metal is artificially stimulated. As the oxide layer develops, the aluminium anode gradually diminishes, and the oxide front progresses into the structure, generating fresh oxide at the interface between the metal and the oxide [59]. Consequently, the expansion of the anodic layer is closely linked to the microstructure of the structure [59]. The layer of Al_2O_3 that forms during the anodization process has a porous form, which makes it the perfect candidate for acting as a catalyst structure, to which catalyst particles can stick into [58]. This process results in the creation of a hexagonal cell structure that is organized and arranged on its own [60]. Each cell in this structure is closed at the bottom and has a central pore that runs from the base to the top of the cell. The structure of said cells can be seen in Figure 5. The thickness of the cell wall and the diameter of the pore are determined by many parameters, such as applied voltage, current and anodization time [50].

Figure 5. Structure of anodized structure layer. Reproduced from Scampone *et al.* [61].

3.1 Anodization parameters

3.1.1 Electrolyte

The electrolyte serves as the primary conductor in the anodizing process as it enables the movement of ions between the anode, cathode, and across the oxide layer. To ensure efficient anodizing, it is crucial to regulate the accumulation of reaction products that occur during the oxidation of the structure. Excessive accumulation can lead to increased resistance within the electrolyte, resulting in decreased conductivity [58].

Commonly used electrolytes in this process are oxalic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) and chromic acid (H_2CrO_4), but the electrolyte concentration and temperature are commonly varied parameters [58], [60]. Burgos *et al.* [58] concluded that when using either sulfuric acid or oxalic acid, and increasing the electrolyte concentration from 0.4 to 3.2 M, increased the porosity of the alumina. The specific surface area increased from 11.9 to 53.9 $\text{m}^2/\text{g}_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$, while

the value for non-anodized was around 2 - 4 m²/g_{Al}. Same study also reported that the increase of electrolyte temperature from 20 to 40 °C increased the specific surface area from 13.7 to 44.4 m²/g_{Al₂O₃}. Sanz et al. [60] also reported the same, the increase from 0.4 to 1.6 M would increase the specific surface area from 23 to 36 m²/g_{Al₂O₃}. And the increase of temperature from 30 to 50 °C would increase the specific surface area from 4 to 23 m²/g_{Al₂O₃}.

3.1.2 Current density

Studying the effect of electrical current on the anodizing process, it is common to use galvanostatic anodizing. This method involves applying a fixed electrical current while allowing the voltage to fluctuate. It can be useful for studying the electrical response caused by the formation of cracks and voids in the oxide layer. By monitoring the voltage changes over time and comparing them to the behaviour of pure aluminium, defects within the oxide layer can be identified [61].

N. Burgos et al. [58] studied that when current density was increased from 0.5 to 3 A dm⁻², the alumina formation increased with it. The pore volume also increased from 1.31 x 10⁻⁶ to 7.45 x 10⁻⁶ m³_{pore}/m²_{Al}. However, the specific surface area decreases with increased current. Sanz et al. [60] also reported the same results, that increasing the current from 1 to 3 A dm⁻² would increase the pore volume while decreasing the specific surface area. Although the specific surface area of alumina decreases, it was also reported that this reduction is largely offset by the increase in the overall amount of alumina generated.

3.1.3 Voltage

The voltage used in the anodizing process plays a crucial role in the early formation of the anodic layer. It primarily determines the thickness of the barrier layer, which increases proportionally with the applied voltage [60]. In potentiostatic anodizing, where the electrical voltage is controlled during the

process, while current is let to adapt to the system, the applied voltage not only affects the barrier layer but also influences the growth of the porous layer [62]. Too high current can however impair the formation of the oxide layer, so the right balance must be found. As the voltage increases, the oxide layer becomes thicker due to the higher electrical current flowing in the anodizing system. This leads to an exponential growth of the current density and an increase in the rate of oxide growth [58].

Pu et al. [63] reported that increasing the voltage from 20 V to 60 V, while keeping the other parameters constant increased the forming oxide layer thickness from 70 to 110 μm . However, it was also reported that the increased voltage could possibly disrupt the orderly porous morphology of the oxide layer.

3.1.4 Anodizing time

The growth of the oxide layer depends heavily on the anodizing time. Longer anodizing times result in a thicker anodic layer. However, there is a limit to this growth. Once the growth rate of the oxide is balanced by its dissolution rate within the electrolyte, the oxide layer stabilizes, and it cannot become thicker over time [52]. Prolonged anodizing times can decrease the quality of the layer. The outer surface of the anodic layer experiences greater heating effects, raising the local temperature of the electrolyte and increasing its reactivity. This leads to defects and porosity formation on the external surface of the anodic layer, reducing its hardness and wear resistance [61].

This has been confirmed by various studies, such as Burgos et al. [58], where they reported the specific surface area of alumina rose from 36.3 to 70.0 $\text{m}^2/\text{g}_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$ after 30 minutes. But after 50 minutes it had decreased back to 55 $\text{m}^2/\text{g}_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$ due to the oxide dissolution. Also Sanz et al. [60] reported that up to 80 minutes, the anodization time increased the quality of the oxide layer and after this the anodization layer started cracking.

3.2 Anodization post-treatment

The anodization process typically generates an anodized aluminium oxide (AAO) layer that is predominantly porous, exhibiting a significant surface area. In catalyst applications, a high active surface area is generally advantageous [58]. Therefore, it is recommended to employ pore widening treatments. These treatments involve subjecting the aluminium oxide layer to an environment that promotes the dissolution of the aluminium oxide layer, rather than its further growth. A common pore widening treatment (PWT) is treating the structure with the same solution that the anodization was made [64]. This induces the pores of AAO to etch away, thus widening them, like can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The process of anodization and pore widening treatment. Reproduced from Linga Reddy *et al.* [64].

AAO layer can undergo additional treatments to enhance its surface area. One such treatment is a hot water treatment (HWT), which is conducted following the pore widening treatment [64]. During the HWT, the structure is immersed in near-boiling water, allowing for further modifications to the AAO layer. According to Ganley et al. [65], HWT induces hydration of select pores within the AAO layer, leading to a transformation of the existing α -alumina into γ -alumina. This transformation results in an increased surface area of the AAO layer. However, it was also reported that there is a potential risk associated with hydration, as it may cause certain pores to seal up, ultimately reducing the overall surface area of the AAO layer. Zhou et al. [66] documented the ability of the HWT to expand the pores within the AAO and result in a notable enhancement in the BET surface area. Specifically, the surface area increased from an initial value of 16.5 g/m² to a significantly larger value of 204.6 g/m².

4 Catalyst coating

With the completion of the porous aluminium oxide layer, it now becomes possible to introduce a catalytically active material into it. This can be accomplished by either depositing the morphological support or by applying a surface coating with catalytic functionality.

4.1 Slurry coating

According to Schühle et al. [53], slurry coating is deposition method, with a defining feature being the use of a slurry – a suspension of solid particles in a liquid. The solid particles can be the active catalyst materials, often combined with a binder to ensure they adhere well to the structure. The liquid component acts as a carrier for the particles, helping to evenly disperse them and allowing for controlled application to the structure.

In the slurry coating of monolithic structure, the deposition of the coating layer primarily occurs on the channel walls of the support. This technique provides several advantages, including reduced diffusion distances for reactants within the channels and the ability to achieve maximum coating loading without limitations imposed by the monolith macropore volume. However, when the particles employed in the slurry coating process are excessively large, they have the potential to obstruct the pores, resulting in a reduction of the active surface area [44]. To achieve these benefits, slurry coating involves utilizing a slurry consisting of particles that closely match the size of the larger macropores in the support material, typically measuring a few micrometres in diameter. According to Nijhuis et al. [45], the fundamental principle of slurry coating entails combining relatively large particles intended for coating with significantly smaller binder particles. The resulting slurry is then applied onto the walls of the monolith channels and subjected to a drying process. Initially, as the liquid

component evaporates, only the larger particles come into contact with each other. However, as the remaining liquid evaporates, capillary forces come into play and draw the smaller binder particles to the locations where the larger particles make contact. This mechanism that can be seen in Figure 7, ensures that the binder particles are distributed effectively in the desired areas, promoting proper adhesion between the coated particles and the structure.

Figure 7. Representation of drying steps of slurry coating. Reproduced from Nijhuis *et al.* [45].

4.2 Impregnation

Impregnation refers to a process wherein the support material comes into physical contact with a liquid solution containing the catalytically active phase [44]. This contact promotes the migration of the liquid phase onto the support through chemico-physical interactions. In most cases, impregnation follows procedures like anodization, oxide deposition, or other methods to create a porous support on metallic structures. There are two distinct methods of impregnation depending on the solution volume: wet impregnation and incipient wetness impregnation [43].

Wet impregnation involves immersing the structure in a diluted solution containing the dissolved active phase precursor, which often is a salt of the active metal [67]. Excess liquid is then blown out using pressurized air after withdrawal. To prevent uneven distribution due to gravity, the wet structure should be kept horizontally rotated. Subsequently, drying and calcination are typically performed to eliminate the absorbed solvent, impurities, and to form the catalytically active species. This process can be repeated multiple times to better promote phase loading. The amount of active phase precursor added to the impregnating solution is calculated to achieve the desired active phase loading, assuming that the precursor is completely transferred to the support by the end of the process [44].

On the other hand, incipient wetness impregnation, also known as dry impregnation, involves preparing a solution containing the active phase in an amount equal to the pore volume of the support to be impregnated. The solution is then gradually applied drop by drop until the entire pore volume is filled [68]. This method ensures that all the active phase in the solution is deposited without any loss. Precise control is required during the operation, and if the precursor's solubility limits the maximum active phase loading, repeated applications of the solution may be necessary [43]. Similar to wet impregnation, drying and calcination usually follow incipient wetness impregnation.

To facilitate the occupation of pores by the liquid phase, it is necessary to eliminate the presence of air within them. When the pore size is extremely small,

the capillary pressure can exceed the pressure exerted by the trapped air, resulting in the dissolution or escape of air through the solid material [46]. This process can be seen in the Figure 8, for both wet and dry impregnation.

Figure 8. The acting forces present in wet impregnation (a) and dry impregnation (b). Reproduced from Wiley *et al.* [46]

A commonly followed procedure for impregnating a Cu-Zn catalyst into an AAO structure can be achieved by submerging the structure into a solution of catalyst precursors for a set time. Subsequently, any excess solution on the substrate is removed using compressed air. The structure is then dried in the oven and afterwards calcinated in high temperature. This process can be repeated to help achieve a higher catalyst activity [52].

4.3 Deposition–precipitation

Rather than utilizing the conventional method of impregnating the support with a catalyst precursor solution and subsequently decomposing it through thermal treatments, an alternative technique called deposition-precipitation can be employed [44]. In this method, the catalyst precursor is transferred from the solution to the support through controlled precipitation. One advantage of this approach is that it allows for the deposition of an insoluble salt

of the catalyst precursor during the precipitation step. This deposited salt becomes immobilized on the support and remains unaffected by subsequent thermal treatments.

The deposition-precipitation method comprises two consecutive processes. Initially, solutions are prepared using an appropriate amount of precursor salt to achieve the desired loading of the active phase [46]. Subsequently, hydroxyl ions, often in a form of an alkali solution, or by a hydrolysis of urea is introduced to induce the precipitation of the salt. It is essential to prevent precipitation in the bulk solution as it would lead to the deposition of large particles outside the pores of the support, resulting in a catalytic material with poor activity. To avoid this, the nucleation rate at the surface of the support must be higher than that in the bulk solution, while maintaining the homogeneity of the solution. Despite this, weakening of structure is inevitable, especially when stirring is used.

4.4 Co-precipitation

Co-precipitation is a catalyst coating method similar to deposition-precipitation, which ensures the uniform distribution of active species on the catalyst surface, enhancing its effectiveness in catalytic processes. According to Montebelli et al. [44], in the co-precipitation method, multiple solutions (precursors) containing different metal cations are combined. Subsequently, a solution containing a precipitating agent is added to the mixture. This agent triggers a reaction that leads to the formation of a solid precipitate. The resulting precipitate is a mixed-metal compound or composite, incorporating all the cations from the initial solutions. The cations, which will ultimately form the active catalytic sites, are thoroughly and evenly mixed at the molecular level. This precipitate is then separated, often by centrifugation or filtration, and then dried. The resulting solid is then typically calcined, a process which involves heating to high temperatures in the presence of oxygen to remove any

remaining precipitating agent or other impurities and to convert the precipitate to a more stable form, often a mixed metal oxide. The prepared catalyst material can then be applied as a coating to the desired structure. This could be done by dipping the structure into a slurry of the catalyst and then drying it, or the catalyst material might be dispersed in a suitable solvent and sprayed onto the structure. The coated structure is often calcined again to ensure strong adhesion of the catalyst layer to the substrate and to activate the catalyst. This means that it might not be the most adaptable technique in coating complex substrates.

During coprecipitation, various aspects including chemical phases, dispersion, surface area of the active phase, porous structure, particle size, and shape are simultaneously generated. This occurs through controlled agglomeration of primary and secondary units. The resulting features are highly influenced by process conditions such as the type and manner of ingredient dosing, as well as the mixing and stirring methods employed [46].

4.5 Ion exchange

Ion exchange is a widely employed method for the preparation of supported catalysts, especially for the creation of catalyst coatings [44]. This process involves the substitution of ions within a porous support material with ions of the desired active catalyst component.

According to Montebelli et al. [44], the ion exchange process begins with a support material, such as AAO, that possesses ions capable of being exchanged. The support material is immersed in a solution containing the metal ions that will constitute the active component of the catalyst. These metal ions are attracted to the negatively charged framework of the support material, displacing the existing cations and binding to the support.

After the exchange takes place, the resulting material is separated from the solution and subjected to drying. Subsequently, the metal ions within the support material can be converted into the catalytically active form through calcination. This leads to the formation of metal oxide clusters that serve as the active sites for the catalyst. Although most of the ion-exchange procedures are meant for conventional particle catalysts, they can generally be applied to monolithic catalysts as well [45].

4.6 Electrochemical deposition

Electrochemical deposition (ECD), also known as electrodeposition, is a technique widely employed for the synthesis of catalyst coatings, particularly in applications such as fuel cells and electrolyzers [44]. The fundamental principle of this method involves the application of an electric potential to facilitate the reduction of metal cations present in a solution, causing them to deposit as a metallic or metal compound layer onto a conductive structure or support [44].

According to Linga et al. [64] the process begins by immersing a conductive structure into an electrolyte solution containing the metal ions that will serve as the active species in the catalyst. The structure is then connected to the negative terminal (cathode) of a power supply, while an inert electrode, often composed of platinum wire or a carbon rod, is connected to the positive terminal (anode). Upon applying an electric potential across the electrodes, the metal cations present in the solution undergo reduction at the surface of the structure. This reduction process involves the gain of electrons by the metal cations, resulting in their deposition onto the structure as a metallic or metal oxide layer, thereby forming the desired catalyst coating.

One advantage of electrochemical deposition is its ability to directly deposit catalysts onto complex structures, such as porous electrodes, which can be

challenging to achieve with other deposition methods [69]. However, this technique does require a conductive structure, and the deposition of certain materials or the precise control of the deposition process to achieve desired catalyst properties may pose challenges [69].

4.7 Electroless plating

Electroless deposition (ELP) is an autocatalytic chemical method used to deposit metal particles onto a material without needing external electricity, like in electrochemical deposition [46]. It is also sometimes referred as Reduction Deposition Precipitation (RDP). This method has benefit of forming a homogeneous layer even on complex shapes, while also being cost-effective. However, it does have the fundamental problem of the solution being thermodynamically unstable, meaning that the reaction may succeed irreversibly [46].

The process comprises of discharge of an electron by the way of anodic oxidation of reduction agent, which then leads to the cathodic reduction of the metal ion, resulting in the surface substance to receive a metal deposition [70]. In the event of copper deposition, the reaction would be the following Equation (4).

Overall, electroless plating offers advantages such as the ability to coat non-conductive structures and to produce highly uniform and adherent coatings, even on complex or irregularly shaped structures [46]. However, the process does require careful control and monitoring due to the simultaneous occurrence of several reactions and the sensitivity of the plating solutions to impurities [70].

5 Materials and methods

5.1 Experiment setup

The experimental investigations were conducted with "PPFR1," a Pressurized Plug Flow Reactor. This reactor setup featured a fluidized sand bath serving as the heat control for the reactor, designed to maintain precise control over the experimental conditions. A visual representation of the reactor setup can be observed in Figures 9 and 10, and for further clarity, a Process and Instrumentation (P&I) diagram is detailed in Appendix A.

The reactor itself was constructed in-house, engineered with a stainless-steel piping with outer diameter of 12 mm, and inner diameter of 10 mm, which was chosen for its robustness and suitability for accommodating pressurized reaction conditions. To circumvent any issues related to condensation, both the inlet and outlet piping of the reactor were equipped with insulated heating elements, each set to 200°C to ensure that condensation did not interfere with the reaction processes.

Within this experimental setup, the reactors temperature was controlled by a Techne SBS-4 fluidized sand temperature bath, which is also presented in Figure 9. Sand bath was chosen instead of oil bath, due to the messiness of oil baths. The fluidized sand bath provided a precise and uniform heating to the reactor, due to the fluidized state of the sand and the ability to heat the sand thoroughly height-wise.

Figure 9. The reactor setup of fluidized sand bath with the reactor submerged into the sand with inlet and outlet piping sticking out of the sand.

Figure 10. Another view of the reactor system.

The control of gas flow rates to the reactor was executed with the use of Bronkhorst F-201CV thermal mass flow controllers, all regulated through the control terminal. In order to ensure the accuracy in gas flow measurements, calibration procedures were carried out on the mass flow controllers prior to the initiation of the experiments. All the other valves within the system were manually operated. To accurately monitor the temperature within the reactor, a thermocouple was employed. The thermocouple, specifically used for reactor temperature measurements, was inserted from the uppermost section of the reactor, positioned as close as feasible to the catalyst structure. This approach ensured precise temperature measurements and facilitated the control of the reaction environment. Furthermore, the analysis of gas compositions was achieved by means of an Agilent 6890N Gas Chromatograph (GC), shown in Figure 11. Regular biweekly calibration procedures were carried out on the GC instrument, utilizing a calibration gas mixture supplied by AGA AB, which composition is shown in Appendix B. The experiments were run in the same

conditions for each catalyst, constant pressure of 20 bar(g), temperatures of 221, 235 and 250 °C, and the volumetric flow rates of 0.4, 0.8 and 1.2 l/min, with reactant gas composition of $\frac{H_2}{CO_2} = 3$.

Figure 11. The Agilent 6890N Gas Chromatograph used in analysing the gas compositions.

5.2 Execution of experiments

5.2.1 Catalyst preparation

In total five catalysts were prepared by impregnating anodized aluminium structures, which can be seen in Figure 12. The structure was manufactured by 3D-printing, using a AlSi10Mg -alloy. The void fraction of the structure was 0.7 – 0.8, and it was achieved by having an open cellular diamond lattice pattern. It also had a geometric surface area to volume ratio of 800 m²/m³.

Figure 12. Bare 3D-printed aluminium structure with match to scale.

The aluminium structures were anodized in advance and treated with the pore widening treatment and hot water treatment before the impregnation process. The process for the impregnation was adopted from Kim et al. [52]. All five catalysts were prepared with slightly different conditions and the differences are shown in Table 1. The general recipe preparation started with mixing $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in distilled water until the substrates were fully dissolved. The finished solution is shown in the Figure 13.

Table 1. Structure impregnation conditions.

	CAT-1	CAT-2	CAT-3	CAT-4	CAT-5
	Default	High molarity	More immersions	Longer immersion	Optimized conditions
Molarity of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M)	1	2	1	1	2
Molarity of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M)	1	2	1	1	1.5
Precursor ratio (Cu/Zn)	1	1	1	1	0.75
Impregnation length (min)	15	15	15	60	15
Times impregnated	3	3	5	3	5
Catalyst weight (g)	0.567	0.834	0.569	0.304	1.335

Figure 13. A) The impregnation solution of copper(II) nitrate trihydrate and zinc nitrate hexahydrate in distilled water with structure submerged. B) The Naber 2804 muffle furnace used in the drying and calcination processes of impregnations.

The structure was carefully lowered into the solution and subjected to varying immersion durations, either 15 or 60 minutes, based on the specific catalyst prepared. To ensure an even and thorough coating, the structure was rotated periodically within the solution. Following the designated impregnation period, the structure was delicately withdrawn from the solution, allowing the excess solution to naturally drain away. Any residual solution clinging to the substrate was then eliminated using compressed air, guaranteeing that the drying catalyst particles wouldn't block the channels.

The next step involved placing the structure inside a preheated Naber 2804 muffle furnace, shown in Figure 13. B), set to a temperature of 200 °C, and allowing it to undergo a drying process that lasted 60 minutes. After the drying phase, the structure was removed from the furnace and allowed to cool to room temperature. Subsequently, the structure's mass was measured to determine the catalyst mass increase, with the obtained data presented in Table 2. The submerging and drying sequence was then repeated between 3 to 5 times.

Table 2. Mass increase of impregnated structures.

	CAT-1	CAT-2	CAT-3	CAT-4	CAT-5
Blank weight (g)	4,368	4,293	4,110	4,289	4,250
1. round weight (g)	4,710	4,723	4,190	4,391	4,627
2. round weight (g)	4,971	5,069	4,380	4,587	5,052
3. round weight (g)	5,044	5,423	4,641	4,740	5,416
4. round weight(g)	-	-	4,836	-	5,875
5. round weight (g)	-	-	4,708	-	6,085
Final weight (g)	4,935	5,127	4,678	4,593	5,585
Catalyst weight (g)	0,567	0,834	0,569	0,304	1,335

Following the final drying cycle, the muffle furnace temperature was increased to 350 °C. The structure was then subjected to calcination in the furnace, where total decomposition of precursors is performed, and a stable oxide system is formed. The calcination process lasts for a duration of three hours, after which the furnace was powered down and allowed to cool naturally overnight,

mitigating any potential thermal stresses that could affect the structure. The readymade catalyst and the structure between submersions are shown in the Figure 14.

Figure 14. Catalyst structure at specific stages of the impregnation process. A: The readymade impregnated catalyst after the calcination. B: The substrate after the final impregnation repetition. C-E: The structure after first, second and third impregnation process.

The Figure 14. shows that the homogeneity of visible catalyst at the structure was prominently uniform, although at times random. The inconsistency most

likely was caused by the concentration difference of the impregnation solution within the structure.

Like it can be seen from the Tables 1 and 2, the longer impregnation times were not effective at adding catalyst mass. Contrarily, higher molarity of the solution, increase in impregnation rounds and lowering the ratio of precursors all increased the gained catalyst mass onto the structure.

5.2.2 Reaction experiments

The GC was first calibrated by taking six samples from the calibration gas bottle, to calibrate the CO, CO₂, H₂ and N₂ gases. Then the reactor was assembled. As the inner diameter of the steel pipe and the outer diameter of the structure were both 10 mm, the aluminum structure had to sanded down manually with sandpaper, in order to achieve smaller diameter. The loose structure was then blown away with compressed air, and finally fit into the reactor. The reactor was then connected to the piping with Swagelok connections. Preliminary pressure test was done under 1 bar(g), employing nitrogen gas. This preliminary test was essential to identify any potential leaks within the system by monitoring for pressure drops. Subsequent to the successful completion of the preliminary test, a secondary test was conducted under 20 bar(g) pressure to further assess the reactor's capacity to withstand higher pressures.

To prepare the catalyst for use, a reduction process was implemented, where the metal oxides are converted into their metallic forms, thus activating the catalysts surface properties. The initial step involved elevating the temperature within the reactor to 100 °C. Subsequently, a flow of nitrogen gas was introduced into the reactor, followed by the introduction of H₂ into the reactor as flow of 0.09 l/min. The reactor's temperature was then raised to 250 °C within 30 minutes, where it was maintained for a duration of one hour. The whole reduction process was performed at atmospheric pressure. Following this

reduction period, the temperature was gradually lowered, and the supply of hydrogen gas was terminated.

The experimental procedures were initiated as follows: Initially, the GC was activated and programmed to perform periodic sampling, with GC samples collected at 12-minute intervals. Subsequently, the temperature of the reactor was systematically elevated within the range of 221 to 250 °C, while also increasing the system pressure to 20 bar(g).

Upon achieving the desired operating conditions, the gas valves controlling the flow of H₂, N₂, and CO₂ were opened and configured to enable gas flow through the reactor bypass. The composition of the gas stream was then adjusted via the control terminal to achieve a $\frac{H_2}{CO_2} = 3$, with 7.5% of N₂ serving as the balance gas, thereby achieving a volumetric flow rate ranging between 0.4 and 1.2 l/min.

Subsequently, the volumetric gas flow of the incoming gases was measured using a gas meter. Following this measurement, a total of six samples were taken from the incoming gases employing the GC. Following the acquisition of the initial samples, the incoming gases were redirected from the bypass and introduced into the reactor. Subsequently, a total of 25 samples were extracted from the product gases using the GC for analysis. After the product samples, the gas flow of products was measured using a gas meter. When the experiment was finished, the system was flushed with N₂. Then the pressure and temperature were brought back down, and GC was set to a standby setting.

5.3 Calculation methods

The results of the experiments were calculated using the data obtained from the TCD-GC. The results that were analysed were the conversion of CO₂ and H₂, selectivity of MeOH and CO, yield of MeOH and specific activity of MeOH.

Molar flowrates of reactants was calculated using the Equation 5.

$$\dot{n}_i = \frac{V\%_i \dot{V}_{tot}}{V_M} \quad (5)$$

$V\%_i$ = Volumetric percentage of component i in reactants

\dot{V}_{tot} = Total volumetric flow rate [dm³ min⁻¹] at STP

V_M = Molar volume, 22,414 dm³ mol⁻¹ at STP

Conversion of CO₂ and H₂ were calculated using the molar flow rates, using the Equation 6.

$$X_i = \frac{\dot{n}_{i,IN} - \dot{n}_{i,OUT}}{\dot{n}_{i,IN}} = 1 - \frac{\dot{n}_{i,OUT}}{\dot{n}_{i,IN}} \quad (6)$$

$\dot{n}_{i,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ or H₂ in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{i,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ or H₂ in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

Similarly, the selectivity of CO was calculated from the GC data, using the Equation 7. The selectivity of MeOH in turn was calculated using Equation 8, assuming that no other reactions would be present, and no other undesired products would be produced, like the Equations 1-3 show.

$$S_{CO} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO,OUT}}{X_{CO_2}} \quad (7)$$

$\dot{n}_{CO,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of CO in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO_2,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

X_{CO_2} = Conversion of CO₂

$$S_{MeOH} = 100\% - S_{CO} \quad (8)$$

S_{CO} = Selectivity of CO [%]

The yield of MeOH can be calculated multiple ways, but commonly used method is using conversion and selectivity, as can be seen in the Equation 9 and 10.

$$Y_{MeOH} = X_{CO_2} \cdot S_{MeOH} \quad (9)$$

$$X_{CO_2} = \text{Conversion of } CO_2 \text{ [\%]}$$

$$S_{MeOH} = \text{Selectivity of MeOH [\%]}$$

$$Y_{CO} = X_{CO_2} S_{CO} \quad (10)$$

$$X_{CO_2} = \text{Conversion of } CO_2 \text{ [\%]}$$

$$S_{CO} = \text{Selectivity of CO [\%]}$$

Specific activity of catalyst was also calculated using Equation 11, which determines the catalyst activity on a basis of mass.

$$SA_{MeOH} \left(\frac{m_{MeOH}}{m_{cat}} h \right) = \frac{\dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT} \cdot M_{MeOH} \cdot 60}{m_{cat}} \quad (11)$$

$$SA_{MeOH} = \text{Specific activity of MeOH} \left[\frac{m_{MeOH}}{m_{catalyst}} h \right]$$

$$m_{MeOH} = \text{Mass of methanol [g]}$$

$$\dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT} = \text{Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor outlet [mol min}^{-1}\text{]}$$

$$M_{MeOH} = \text{Molar mass of MeOH [g mol}^{-1}\text{]}$$

$$m_{MeOH} = \text{Mass of methanol [g]}$$

$$m_{cat} = \text{Mass of catalyst achieved by impregnation [g]}$$

To help to verify the accuracy of the results, the elemental balances were calculated using Equations 12, 13 and 14.

$$C_{balance} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO,OUT} + \dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT} + \dot{n}_{CO_2,OUT}}{\dot{n}_{CO,IN} + \dot{n}_{MeOH,IN} + \dot{n}_{CO_2,IN}} \quad (12)$$

$\dot{n}_{CO,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of CO in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{MeOH,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO_2,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of CO in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO_2,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$$H_{balance} = \frac{2\dot{n}_{H_2,OUT} + 4\dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT} + \dot{n}_{H_2O,OUT}}{2\dot{n}_{H_2,IN} + 4\dot{n}_{MeOH,IN}} \quad (13)$$

$\dot{n}_{H_2,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of H₂ in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{MeOH,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{H_2,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of H₂ in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{H_2O,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of H₂O in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$$O_{balance} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO,OUT} + \dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT} + 2\dot{n}_{CO_2,OUT} + \dot{n}_{H_2O,OUT}}{\dot{n}_{CO,IN} + \dot{n}_{MeOH,IN} + 2\dot{n}_{CO_2,IN}} \quad (14)$$

$\dot{n}_{CO,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of CO in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{MeOH,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO_2,IN}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ in the reactor inlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of CO in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{MeOH,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of MeOH in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{CO_2,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of CO₂ in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

$\dot{n}_{H_2O,OUT}$ = Molar flow rate of H₂O in the reactor outlet [mol min⁻¹]

6 Results and discussion

6.1 Commercial particle catalyst and CAT- 1-4

Since commercial particle catalyst was previously used on the reactor, a blank run was performed to ensure that the reaction system worked as expected and that there was nothing within the system or bare structure that could catalyse a reaction. A bare aluminium structure was used in the blank run, where used temperature was 235 °C, pressure was 20 bar(g), and flow rate was 0.8 l/min. The results for the blank run and similarly run commercial catalyst, are presented in the Figure 15, which shows the yields of MeOH and CO.

Figure 15. MeOH and CO yields of commercial particle catalyst (left) and blank aluminium structure (right) in same conditions. The blank structure showed no apparent catalyst activity.

As it can be seen in the Figure 15, there is no MeOH or CO formation in the blank run, indicating that the system works properly and there are no catalyst traces left in the system, or anything else that could have catalysed the reaction, thus influencing the later results.

Four impregnated Cu/Zn/Al₂O₃ -structures, CAT-1, CAT-2, CAT-3 and CAT-4 were run in order to determine the most suitable recipe for the impregnation and for running conditions of MeOH synthesis. The conversion of CO₂ and the selectivity of MeOH between the commercial catalysts and coated catalysts of CAT- 1-4 are shown in the Figures 16. and 17. The complete result data of these experiments are presented in the Appendix C.

Figure 16. Particle catalyst and coated catalysts conversions of CO₂. A) Shows the conversions at volumetric flow rate of 0.4 l/min. B) Shows the conversions at volumetric flow rate of 1.2 l/min.

Figure 16. shows that the particle catalyst has a much higher conversions of CO₂ when compared to the coated ones. This could be explained by the higher catalyst mass of the particle catalyst. The figure also shows that both the particle and coated catalysts follow the same trend of rising with the increasing temperature.

Figure 17. Particle catalyst and coated catalysts selectivity of MeOH. A) Shows the selectivity at volumetric flow rate of 0.4 l/min. B) Shows the selectivity at volumetric flow rate of 1.2 l/min.

Figure 17. shows that particle catalyst has a similar trend and scale as the coated catalysts with the increasing temperature.

6.2 Scanning electron microscope results

A Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was employed to assess the efficacy and outcomes of structure pre-treatment tests (anodization, PWT and HWT procedures) and wet-impregnation. The scan of the bare anodized structure and impregnated structure is shown in the Figure 18.

Figure 18. A) The scanning electron microscope results of the anodized aluminium structure at 200 times magnification. B) Shows the scanning electron

microscope results of the impregnated catalyst structure at 200 times magnification.

Figure 18.A illustrates the surface characteristics of the structure, revealing a smooth texture. This observation suggests that the anodization process, encompassing PWT and HWT, aimed at generating porosity, did not yield the intended results. In best scenario, the surface should exhibit visible pores, however, upon observing at the micron scale, this phenomenon did not occur, indicating the potential presence of either sub-micron scale porosity or the absence of porosity entirely.

As depicted in Figure 18.B, the impregnation process has yielded successful results. The surface of the structure exhibits a discernibly irregular texture, contrasting with the smoothness present in Figure 16.A This disparity is indicative of the effective deposition of the Cu/Zn catalyst onto the structure's surface. Furthermore, the figure reveals a uniform distribution of the gained catalyst, signifying that potential channel blockages within the present aluminum bulk-structure, a prior concern, have been mitigated. This uniformity ensures that the passage of gases remains free from the formation of preferential pathways. Furthermore, any potential micron-scale porosity was obscured beneath the impregnation layer.

6.3 Effect of temperature

For the final impregnated substrate, CAT-5, 11 runs were performed, with the same range as tested but with additional conditions than the previous catalysts. The results for these runs are presented in the Table 3. and more accurately in this chapter.

Table 3. The results of the experiments using CAT-5 catalyst.

Running number	37	38	39	40	41
Temperature (°C)	250	250	235	221	235
Flow rate (l/min)	0.4	1.2	0.8	1.2	0.4
avg X(CO ₂) %	8.4	2.9	3.1	1	6.3
avg X(H ₂) %	6.9	1.9	2.6	1	5.1
avg S(CO) %	67.3	89.8	83	58.2	51.1
AVG S(MeOH) %	32.7	10.2	17	41.8	48.9
AVG Y(MeOH) %	2.74	0.3	0.53	0.43	3.09
AVG Y(CO)	5.63	2.64	2.6	0.6	3.23
SA (MeOH) g/gcat*h	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.02
Running number	42	43	44	45	46
Temperature (°C)	235	221	250	221	235
Flow rate (l/min)	1.2	0.8	0.8	0.4	0.8
avg X(CO ₂) %	2.1	1.4	4.6	2.4	2.1
avg X(H ₂) %	2	1.7	3.9	3.2	2
avg S(CO) %	45.5	39.8	65.7	43	59.4
AVG S(MeOH) %	54.5	60.2	34.3	57	40.6
AVG Y(MeOH) %	1.12	0.84	1.58	1.38	0.87
AVG Y(CO)	0.94	0.56	3.03	1.04	1.28
SA (MeOH) g/gcat*h	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02

The figure depicting simple linear regression model for CO₂ conversion as a function of temperature for different flow rates is shown in Figure 19. Conversions were calculated with the Equation 5.

Figure 19. Simple linear regression analysis depicting the relationship between CO₂ conversion and reaction temperature with different volumetric flow rates. ($Q=0.4$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.962$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=0.8$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.899$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=1.2$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.996$; confidence=0.95)

As the Figure 19. shows, reaction temperature and the conversion of CO₂ has a positive correlation, meaning that the increase in reaction temperature increases the total conversion of CO₂, despite the change of flow rate, although it does not show the spread between MeOH and CO.

The figures depicting the simple linear regression models for CO and MeOH selectivity as a function of temperature for different flow rates are shown in the Figures 20 and 21. The selectivity of CO was calculated with Equation 7, while selectivity of MeOH was calculated using Equation 8.

Figure 20. Simple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between selectivity of CO and temperature with 0.4 l/min and 0.8 l/min flow rates. ($Q=0.4$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.960$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=0.8$ l/min, $N=4$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.908$; confidence=0.95)

Figure 21. Multiple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between selectivity of MeOH and temperature with 0.4 l/min and 0.8 l/min flow rates. ($Q=0.4$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.971$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=0.8$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.908$; confidence=0.95)

It is evident that the formation of MeOH exhibits a preference for lower temperatures, with the highest selectivity for MeOH being achieved at 221°C. Conversely, rWGS demonstrates a bias for higher temperatures. This phenomenon can be interpreted by examining Figures 20 and 21, which illustrate that the selectivity of CO displays a positive correlation with rising temperature, while the selectivity of MeOH exhibits a negative correlation with increasing temperature. As the regression correlation of 1.2 l/min flow rate was poor, it has not been considered in the previous figures.

The figures presenting the simple linear regression models for MeOH and CO yield as a function of temperature are shown in the Figures 22 and 23.

The yield of MeOH was calculated using Equation 9, while yield of CO was calculated with Equation 10.

Figure 22. Simple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between the yield of MeOH with respect to the temperature of the reaction at different flow rates. ($Q=0.4$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.547$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=0.8$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.499$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=1.2$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.457$; confidence=0.95)

Figure 23. Multiple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between the yield of CO with respect to the temperature of the reaction with

different flow rates. ($Q=0.4$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.999$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=0.8$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.769$; confidence=0.95), ($Q=1.2$ l/min, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.883$; confidence=0.95)

As illustrated in Figures 22 and 23, it is evident that the yield of MeOH shows almost no correlation, while CO exhibits a positive correlation with the increase of reaction temperature. Notably, the change in temperature affects the yield of CO more than it does affect the yield of MeOH.

6.4 Effect of flow rate

The figure depicting simple linear regression model for CO₂ conversion as a function of flow rate for different temperatures is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Simple linear regression analysis depicting the relationship between CO₂ conversion and volumetric flow rate at different temperatures. ($T=221$ °C, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.932$; confidence=0.95), ($T=235$ °C, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.759$; confidence=0.95), ($T=250$ °C, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.953$; confidence=0.95)

Figure 24 offers insight into the relationship between volumetric flow rate and CO₂ conversion. It can be deduced that there exists a negative correlation between CO₂ conversion and the flow rate. Specifically, an increase in the

volumetric flow rate is associated with a reduction in residence time, consequently resulting in a decrease in the rate of CO₂ conversion.

The figures depicting the simple linear regression models for CO and MeOH selectivity as a function of volumetric flow rate at different temperatures are shown in the Figures 25 and 26.

Figure 25. Simple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between selectivity of CO and volumetric flow rate at different temperatures. ($T=221\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.598$; confidence=0.95), ($T=250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.696$; confidence=0.95)

Figure 26. Simple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between selectivity of MeOH and volumetric flow rate at different temperatures. ($T=221$ °C, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.598$; confidence=0.95), ($T=250$ °C, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.696$; confidence=0.95)

Figures 25 and 26 provide valuable insights into the selectivity of carbon monoxide (CO) and methanol (MeOH) in response to variations in flow rate. Notably, the data reveals a positive correlation between flow rate and the selectivity of CO, while a negative correlation is observed in the case of MeOH. This suggests that the selectivity of MeOH is more favourable at lower flow rates, specifically at 0.4 l/min, in contrast to the selectivity of CO, which demonstrates a preference for higher flow rates.

These observations collectively signify that shorter diffusion lengths are favoured, and thus there is a presence of internal mass transfer limitations within the system. Additionally, the results indicate that the rWGS-reaction is characterized by a faster reaction rate when compared to the production of MeOH, as reflected by the distinct selectivity patterns with respect to varying flow rates.

The figures presenting the simple linear regression models for MeOH and CO yield as a function of volumetric flow rate at different temperatures are shown in the Figures 27 and 28.

Figure 27. Simple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between the yield of MeOH with respect to the volumetric flow rate at different temperatures. ($T=221\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.995$; confidence=0.95), ($T=235\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.488$; confidence=0.95), ($T=250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.999$; confidence=0.95)

Figure 28. Simple linear regression analysis showing the relationship between the yield of CO with respect to the volumetric flow rate at different

temperatures. ($T=221\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.677$; $\text{confidence}=0.95$), ($T=235\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.859$; $\text{confidence}=0.95$), ($T=250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $N=3$, $df=1$, $R^2=0.847$; $\text{confidence}=0.95$)

Like the Figures of 27 and 28 show, yields of both MeOH and CO have negative correlation with the flow rate, meaning that they both favour the lower flow rates, indicating that the limiting factor is the internal mass transfer.

6.5 Specific activity

Considering that the specific activity for methanol (MeOH) formation primarily depends upon the quantity of catalyst mass, it is insufficient to evaluate the outcomes solely based on CAT-5, where the catalyst mass remains constant. Consequently, an analysis of specific activity requires a comparison between catalysts CAT-1 through CAT-5. The Figure 29 shows the specific activity as the function of catalyst mass.

Figure 29. The relationship between the specific activity of MeOH with respect to the catalyst mass at different conditions.

Figure 29 shows that there seems to be no correlation between catalyst weight and specific activity at all of the different conditions. This can be validated by the observation that the structure lacked pores, and the Cu/Zn particles were effectively impregnating atop one another, thereby leading to an inefficient utilization of the entire catalyst mass. Consequently, the reduced specific activity may be attributed to the incomplete exploitation of the catalyst's potential.

7 Error estimation

7.1 Reactor system

Although the reactor system was quite simple, there were several sources that could potentially cause errors to the results. One of the major sources was the heating of the reactor and the piping, especially because temperature of the system was one of the main conditions that was researched. The sand bath that was used to heat the reactor, had a habit of starting to fluctuate the temperature when ramping up to the set temperature by around 15 °C. But once it reached the wanted temperature, it kept it steadily for the rest of the run, if the fluidization flow rate was kept at proper level.

For most of the CAT-2 experiments, some of the pre-heating of the inlet gases were turned off by the surge protector. But because only some of the piping was left unheated, it didn't have any noticeable effect on the results, as the reactor temperature could still be held steady.

The thermocouple, that was used to measure the temperature of the catalyst surface was most likely not actually measuring the surface of the structure, but some centimetres from it. The reasoning for this was that when building the reactor, the catalyst structure could move somewhat freely within the reactor in the beginning, so the thermocouple couldn't be set to touch the structure with a certainty. This may have caused some differences between the wanted and the measured reaction temperatures.

The mass flow controllers used to control the input gas compositions were sometimes inaccurate when using smaller (0.4 l/min) flow rates, as the H₂ mass flow controller was calibrated for 1 l/min. This caused some of the experiments to not achieve a steady molar ratio of 3 with H₂/CO₂, but rather molar ratio value of 2.3. Said invalid flow rate runs were discarded from the results

and are marked in Appendix C with an asterisk (*). To get around this problem, the input of H₂ gas was increased by 20 %, until $\frac{H_2}{CO_2} = 3$ was achieved.

The elemental balances of oxygen, hydrogen and carbon were calculated to ensure that the results and calculations would be correct. If approximately the same number of elements (± 5 %) would be present in both the inlet gases and the outlet gases, the calculations could be assumed to be correct. If the balances were not adequate, said experiment was discarded and possibly rerun. The balances of CAT-5 experiments are shown in the Table 4.

Table 4. The elemental balances of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen in the CAT-5 experiments.

Run no.	AVG C balance (%)	AVG H balance (%)	AVG O balance (%)
37	97.4	92.8	94.2
38	99.9	98.1	98.4
39	99.6	97.5	98.2
40	99.7	99.0	99.3
41	96.9	94.7	95.1
42	98.9	98.1	98.4
43	99.2	98.4	98.9
44	98.4	96.0	96.8
45	98.6	96.8	98.1
46	99.2	98.0	98.5

Like the Table 4 shows, the elemental balances show maximum of five percent of variation, meaning that mass flow controllers worked evenly, and there were no problems within the gas feed system, and neither any unaccounted leaks.

Only MeOH synthesis and rWGS was accounted to happen in the reaction system. So, if any other reaction happened in the reactor, which product the GC couldn't detect, they would be ignored, and could potentially deviate the results. The GC did detect a small spike in the TCD, in almost every run

experiment. This spike was most likely for dimethyl ether (DME), which can also be produced through MeOH.

7.2 Gas chromatography analysis

The biggest error source was most likely caused by the analytical limitations of the gas chromatography. The small values of the methanol samples posed challenges for accurate detection by the GC. To address this, the reported values represent averages derived from multiple samples. This approach was necessary due to large variance between individual samples, rendering direct comparisons unreliable.

7.3 Deactivation of the catalyst

As the catalyst samples were tested for multiple weeks, some deactivation could be expected. Despite the low temperatures, sintering could happen within the catalyst, and the formation of water would most likely drop the activity of the catalyst. For the CAT-2 and CAT-5, a repeatability test was performed in the same conditions, and the results are shown in the Figure 30 as the relation of time on stream (TOS) versus the conversion of CO₂.

Figure 30. Repeatability tests of CAT-2 and CAT-5 as a conversion of CO₂ as a function of spent catalyst hours.

As the Figure 30 shows, both the CAT-2 and CAT-5 show signs that the conversion of CO₂ steadily decreases when catalyst is used. This leads to some indication of deactivation happening the longer the catalysts are used.

8 Conclusion and suggestions for future studies

The heterogeneous catalytic production of methanol can be produced through CO₂ hydrogenation within the temperature range of 200°C to 300°C and under pressure conditions ranging from 30 to 100 bar. In this operational range, an additional reaction, the reverse water-gas shift, competes with CO₂ hydrogenation, resulting in the conversion of carbon dioxide to carbon monoxide. Copper-based catalysts are conventionally employed in this context. The use of structured catalysts is a relatively novel technology, mainly used in the automotive industry for transforming harmful exhaust gases into less environmentally harmful substances. But it has a lot of advantages due to its mass transfer abilities and lower pressure drops when comparing to particle catalysts.

The overarching objective of this research was to use structured catalysts in the methanol production process through CO₂ hydrogenation, while exploring different catalyst coating techniques. While the study successfully achieved its objectives, it should be noted that only one specific catalyst coating method, wet impregnation, was employed and investigated in practice. Variations of catalysts were generated using this particular approach.

The experimental investigations were executed within a pressurized plug flow reactor, employing a Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ coated catalyst on a anodized aluminum lattice, prepared via the wet-impregnation method. The experimental conditions encompassed temperature ranges of 221°C to 250°C, flow rates ranging from 0.4 to 1.2 liters per minute, and a consistent operating pressure of 20 bar(g).

The coating phase of the experiments achieved success, with the successful impregnation of a solid catalyst layer into the structure. However, when comparing the specific activities of prepared catalyst structures, it shows that the increased number of coating rounds and thus catalyst mass didn't increase the activity of the catalysts structure.

The outcomes of the experiments indicated that the prepared catalysts were effective in catalyzing the conversion of CO₂ into both MeOH and CO. Nevertheless, it became apparent that under the prescribed conditions, CO₂ hydrogenation was slower in comparison to the rWGS. CO yields consistently exceeded over twice the yields of MeOH, underscoring the greater prominence of the former reaction. Additionally, the selectivity of CO surpassed that of MeOH, suggesting that the prepared catalysts did not exhibit a specific preference for favoring MeOH synthesis. The most favorable results for MeOH synthesis were consistently obtained at low temperatures and low flow rates.

The pressure level employed in these experiments was 20 bar(g), which was on the lower level of CO₂ hydrogenation pressure range, dictated by the limitations of the reactor system. The conventional practice for CO₂ hydrogenation employs and is favored by elevated pressures. Consequently, future investigations would be advised to run the experiments at higher pressure conditions.

While the coated structure catalysts in this study did not yield high results for the catalytic activity, they still managed to synthesize MeOH at some level. Meaning that they still retain promise for potential practical applications. Therefore, further assessments and testing are justified to uncover their full potential and improve their catalyst activity.

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Appendices

Appendix A: P&I diagram of the reactor setup

Appendix B: AGA certified calibration gas composition

Compound	Calibration gas (vol-%)
H ₂	32.0
CO	25.0
CO ₂	10.0
CH ₄	8.0
C ₂ H ₄	2.01
C ₂ H ₆	1.0
C ₂ H ₂	1.0
N ₂	20.99

Appendix C: Experimental results of CAT-1, CAT-2, CAT-3 and CAT-4

Running number	T	Q	Catalyst	avg X(CO ₂)	avg X(H ₂)	avg C bal	avg H bal	avg O bal	avg S(CO)	vg S(MeOH)G	S(MeOH)G	Y(MeOH)MeOH	mol(MeOH)	g/gAVG	Y(CO)G	MeOH
13	221	0,4	1	1,35	1,42	1,00	1,01	1,01	71,84	7,45	28,16	0,38	1,92E-05	0,02	0,97	0,10
14	221	1,2	1	0,74	0,75	1,01	1,01	1,01	0,00	7,37	100,00	0,74	9,36E-05	0,02	0,00	0,16
15	250	0,4	1	7,05	5,33	1,02	1,06	1,05	75,10	2,35	24,90	1,76	7,95E-05	0,02	5,30	0,39
16	250	1,2	1	5,86	3,26	1,01	1,03	1,04	82,92	2,92	17,08	1,00	1,20E-04	0,04	4,86	0,22
17	221	0,4	2	5,22	2,99	1,02	1,03	1,04	63,69	6,91	36,31	1,89	7,05E-05	0,02	3,32	0,39
18	250	0,4	2	13,01	9,90	1,02	1,11	1,08	85,01	1,69	14,99	1,95	8,93E-05	0,02	11,06	0,45
19	221	1,2	2	2,97	2,11	1,01	1,02	1,02	74,41	8,64	25,59	0,76	9,30E-05	0,04	2,21	0,17
20	250	1,2	2	11,03	5,21	1,01	1,05	1,06	93,70	2,27	6,30	0,70	7,90E-05	0,03	4,00	0,14
21 (**17)	221	0,4	2	4,00	3,82	1,02	1,04	1,03	53,96	3,07	46,04	1,84	9,11E-05	0,09	2,16	0,47
22 (18*)	250	0,4	2	11,43	6,83	1,01	1,07	1,07	88,80	1,74	11,20	1,28	5,84E-05	0,09	10,15	0,30
23	235	0,8	2	4,44	4,12	0,98	1,00	0,99	78,23	4,17	21,77	0,97	8,15E-05	0,19	3,47	0,22
24 (**23)	235	0,8	2	5,09	2,62	1,00	1,03	1,03	87,95	6,75	12,05	0,61	5,20E-05	0,21	4,47	0,14
25	250	0,4	3	7,29	5,73	1,01	1,06	1,05	79,28	3,20	20,72	1,51	6,96E-05	0,03	5,78	0,38
26	221	0,4	3	2,85	3,80	1,02	1,04	1,02	42,43	3,13	57,57	1,64	7,98E-05	0,02	1,21	0,43
27	221	1,2	3	1,45	1,55	1,01	1,02	1,01	50,96	4,99	49,04	0,71	8,65E-05	0,03	0,74	0,16
28	250	1,2	3	2,85	1,94	1,00	1,02	1,02	84,89	5,09	15,11	0,43	5,08E-05	0,04	2,42	0,10
29	235	0,8	3	2,74	2,53	1,01	1,03	1,02	64,08	4,30	35,92	0,98	8,18E-05	0,17	1,76	0,23
30	221	0,4	4	1,53	2,81	1,00	1,03	1,01	69,07	4,96	30,93	0,47	2,3E-05	0,04	1,06	0,12
31	221	1,2	4	1,06	1,09	1,01	1,01	1,01	0,00	7,36	100,00	1,06	0,000128	0,05	0,00	0,24
32	250	0,4	4	5,67	4,69	1,01	1,05	1,03	79,07	3,72	20,93	1,19	5,61E-05	0,05	4,48	0,30